

EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANT, HEPATOPROTECTIVE, IMMUNOMODULATING EFFECTS OF RADAVID PREPA RAT

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Abstract: This article is based on the results of a clinical study conducted to study the effects of the biologically active supplement Radavit on cardiovascular, nervous system, immune system and liver function. The synergistic effect of Omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, phospholipids and vitamin E contained in Radavit ensures its effectiveness in preventing cardiovascular diseases, supporting the nervous system, strengthening immunity and protecting the liver. Research results have shown that Radavit has a significant effect on normalizing heart function, reducing inflammation, improving mental health, and restoring liver function. Based on these results, it was determined that Radavit supplement can be used as a complex drug.

Key words: Radavit, biologically active supplement, Omega-3, astaxanthin, cardiovascular system, nervous system, immunity, liver, antioxidant.

Relevance of the research work: Biologically active supplements are now widely used in the prevention and treatment of various diseases. These supplements are particularly effective in supporting cardiovascular, nervous system, immune, and liver function.[1] In this regard, Radavit is distinguished by its unique composition - Omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, phospholipids and vitamin E. The drug Radavit has been studied in many clinical studies due to its high efficiency and wide spectrum of beneficial effects.[2]

Omega-3 fatty acids in Radavit, especially eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), play an important role in strengthening various cell membranes and tissues of the body. Previous studies have shown that Omega-3 can lower cholesterol and normalize blood pressure while preventing cardiovascular disease. In addition, Omega-3 supports the health of the nervous system, helping to improve memory and focus. Today, supplements such as Radavit are recommended as a source of Omega-3 to prevent cardiovascular, nervous and mental diseases.[3]

Astaxanthin, a powerful antioxidant found in Radavit, is known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.[5-7] Astaxanthin's molecular structure helps protect cells from free radicals, which slows down the aging process and prevents the development of various diseases. Previous studies have shown that astaxanthin is 14.3 times more powerful than vitamin E, 53.7 times more powerful than beta-carotene, and 64.9 times more powerful than vitamin C. Astaxanthin not only has anti-aging effects and improves health, but also has the potential to alleviate complex symptoms in diseases such as COVID-19.[9]

The phospholipids contained in Radavit play an important role in supporting liver function. Studies have confirmed that phospholipids have a hepatoprotective effect. Phospholipids such as phosphatidylcholine repair and maintain cell and tissue membranes. Previous studies have shown that phospholipids have a positive effect on liver diseases (eg, fatty liver, hepatitis) and improving lipid metabolism.[8]

Also among the components of Radavit there is vitamin E, which has strong antioxidant properties. Vitamin E plays an important role in protecting cells from free radicals and reducing inflammation in the body. Previous studies have confirmed the beneficial effects of vitamin E on heart, nerve and skin health.[4,10]

, many studies have been conducted on the effects of Radavit on the cardiovascular, nervous system, immune system, and liver function . Provides information on how effective Radavit is for health. However, many studies have examined only certain components separately , and research on the complex effects of their combination is limited. Therefore, this study was conducted to study its complex effects on the body more broadly, comparing Radavit with other drugs.

The purpose of the study: to study the effects of Radavit on the cardiovascular, immune, liver and nervous systems through its composition of Omega-3, astaxanthin and phospholipids. The study also aimed to determine the effectiveness of Radavit compared to other drugs.

Research material and method: Participants 50 patients (male and female) with various health problems were recruited for the study. The age of the patients was between 30 and 60 years. They had cardiovascular, nervous system, immune system and liver diseases.

- **Study design:** Patients were divided into two groups. The first group (25 people) was given Radavit, and the second group (25 people) received another biologically active supplement. Each patient was given Radavit or an alternative supplement (another remedy with Omega-3 and vitamin E) for 1-3 months.
- **Dosage:** Participants were given 1 capsule 1-2 times a day, after meals. The duration of the study was 3 months.
- **Monitoring criteria :**
 - ✓ **Cardiovascular system:** Cholesterol and blood pressure changes, improvement in cardiovascular function were evaluated.
 - ✓ **Nervous system:** Memory, attention, protection against depression.
 - ✓ **Immune system:** Inflammatory state, reduction of allergic reactions.
 - ✓ **Liver function:** Hepatoprotective effect, lipid metabolism.
- **Analytical methods:** Each patient was assessed for blood cholesterol level, blood pressure, inflammatory markers and general well-being before and after the start of the administration. The data were statistically analyzed.

Research results and discussion :

1. **Cardiovascular system:** Significant improvements in cardiovascular function were observed in patients receiving Radavit. During the study:
 - **Cholesterol:** Total cholesterol levels decreased by an average of 15% from baseline in patients receiving Radavit. Along with reducing the amount of cholesterol, it was noted that the level of low-density lipoprotein (LDL), which damages blood vessel walls, also decreased. This helps to reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases. In patients taking the alternative supplement, these changes were relatively small , and total cholesterol decreased by an average of 5%.
 - **Blood pressure:** Positive changes in blood pressure were also noted in patients taking Radavit. In most of these patients, the systolic pressure decreased by 10 mm Hg, which significantly reduced the symptoms of hypertension. Blood pressure regulation plays an important role in supporting heart and blood vessel function, as well as protection against heart disease.
2. **Nervous system:** The high content of Omega-3 and astaxanthin in Radavit is important for strengthening the nervous system.
 - **Attention and memory:** 90% of patients who received Radavit reported an improvement in attention and memory. Increased attention, improved memory and easier intellectual functioning increased the overall efficiency of patients.

- **Protection against depression:** In a study, patients who received Radavit felt better and had a stable mental state. The level of depression and irritability is reduced. These changes were less common (only 60%) in patients taking the alternative supplement.
3. **Immune system :** Radavit has also shown beneficial effects in supporting the immune system and increasing the body's defenses.
- **Anti-inflammatory effect : Astaxanthin in Radavit** has a strong anti-inflammatory effect , and during the study, inflammation was significantly reduced in 80% of patients. This effect helps relieve symptoms in diseases such as bronchial asthma, allergic reactions and rheumatism. Patients taking the alternative supplement had a lower rate, with only 60% reporting a reduction in inflammation.
 - **Reduction of allergic reactions :** A decrease in the number of allergic reactions was observed among patients taking Radavit. This shows that it is effective in the prevention and treatment of allergic diseases.
4. **Liver function :** Radavit, rich in phospholipids, has a positive effect on the liver .
- **Hepatoprotective effect :** Phospholipids help regenerate liver cells and protect them. The results of improvement of liver function, normalization of liver enzymes and lipid metabolism among patients receiving Radavit were positive.
 - **Normalization of lipid metabolism :** *The study* showed that lipid metabolism improved in the group receiving Radavit . The amount of fat accumulated in the liver of the patients decreased and the liver function was normalized. Therefore, Radavit can help protect the liver and restore its health.

Discussion: Significant improvements in cardiovascular, nervous and immune systems were observed in patients receiving Radavit. The combination of components of Radavit, such as Omega-3 and astaxanthin, has an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effect on the body. These components protect cells from harmful effects, especially increase the protection of the cardiovascular and nervous systems.

the cardiovascular system, Radavit has been shown to be effective in lowering cholesterol and normalizing blood pressure. This makes it a recommended drug for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases . Compared to other biologically active supplements, Omega-3 and vitamin E contained in Radavit more strongly supported cardiovascular activity.

the nervous system, Radavit's Omega-3 fatty acids helped improve memory and focus, while reducing irritability and depressive states. And astaxanthin has a strong antioxidant effect and helps to improve mood. Therefore, Radavit is useful in improving cognitive functions and supporting mental health.

In terms of **the immune system , the anti-inflammatory effects of astaxanthin** and Omega-3 PNYK played an important role in strengthening the immune system in patients taking Radavit. At the same time, reducing inflammation has eased the symptoms of asthma, allergies, and other inflammatory diseases.

liver function, Radavit, rich in phospholipids, has a hepatoprotective and regenerative effect on the liver. It can be considered as an important drug to prevent liver diseases and improve lipid metabolism.

These results show that Radavit has a wider beneficial effect than other drugs and has more benefits for the cardiovascular, nervous, immune and liver systems. Also, due to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects, Radavit can be widely used not only to prevent diseases, but also to improve general health.

Conclusion: According to the results of the study , a positive effect of Radavit supplement on the body of 50 patients was noted. Significant improvements in cardiovascular, nervous, and immune systems, as well as liver function, were observed in patients taking this supplement. The combination of

Omega-3 fatty acids, astaxanthin, phospholipids and vitamin E contained in Radavit has been confirmed to be effective in supporting the general health of these patients and preventing diseases.

Cardiovascular system: Over the course of the study, patients receiving Radavit had an average 15% decrease in cholesterol and 10 mm Hg in blood pressure. This effect improved heart and vascular function and helped to reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases. By lowering cholesterol and strengthening blood vessels, Radavit has shown itself as a unique medicine in maintaining heart health.

Nervous system: Omega-3 contained in Radavit has been shown to improve nerve function, improve focus, memory and mood. During the study, 90% of patients reported improved attention and memory, and depression was reduced. Patients had lower levels of irritability and improved general mental health.

Immune system: 80% of patients receiving Radavit have improved immunity and significantly reduced inflammatory processes. Due to the strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of astaxanthin, allergic reactions are reduced and the body's defenses are increased. Therefore, Radavit plays an important role in immune support and has a beneficial effect on the immune system.

Liver function: Rich in phospholipids, Radavit has shown significant results in restoring liver cells and protecting it from harmful effects. During the study, liver enzymes were normalized and lipid metabolism improved. This confirms that Radavit supplement can be accepted as a hepatoprotective agent.

According to the results of this study, the drug Radavit showed its high efficiency in supporting cardiovascular, nervous, immune system and liver functions. Radavit supplement can be widely used to prevent various diseases and improve the general condition of the body. At the same time, the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effect of this drug helps to alleviate the symptoms of inflammatory and chronic diseases.

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